

Clay Minerals in Indian Soils

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Studies have been made of the clay minerals present in the clay fractions isolated from some soils of four major Indian soil groups from a consideration of the chemical, X-ray, differential thermal, electrochemical and viscous characteristics developed for the identification of clay mineral components present in their binary and ternary mixtures. The effect of removal of free oxides on the above characteristics of these clays has also been studied.

In previous publications^{1,2} certain criteria based on the the X-ray diffraction, differential thermal, chemical, electrochemical and viscous characteristics of hydrogen forms of clay minerals have been discussed for the identification of clay mineral components present in their binary and ternary mixtures. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to identify the clay minerals present in clays isolated from some soils of the four major Indian soil groups from a consideration of the above criteria. The results obtained have also been compared with corresponding data obtained with oxide free clays³ prepared from the same soils with a view to gaining information on the changes, if any, brought about on the removal of free oxides using the method of Marshall and Jeffries⁴ on the above characteristics of these clays in relation to their clay mineralogy. The details of experimental procedures adopted have been discussed in previous publications^{1,2,3}. The particulars of the soils from which clays have been isolated for this work have been presented in Table I.

TABLE I
Particulars of soils used

No.	Samples	Soil zone	Depth in ins.	Description
1.	Bankura soil (Bankura, West Bengal)	Laterite	0-6"	Yellow in colour, sandy portion higher.
2.	Suri soil (Birbhum, West Bengal)	Laterite	0-6"	Yellow in colour
3.	Bangalore Palace Orchard soil (Bangalore)	Red	0-20"	Red sandy soil
4.	Anantapur soil (Andhra Pradesh)	Red	0-10"	Red sandy soil.
5.	Padegaon soil B-type (Bombay)	Black	0-9"	Black clayey and sticky soil
6.	Kalimpong soil (Darjeeling, West Bengal)	Alluvial	0-6"	Slate coloured clayey soil
7.	Berhampore soil (Murshidabad, West Bengal)	Alluvial	0-6"	Slate coloured soil
8.	Uluberia soil (Howrah, West Bengal)	Alluvial	0-6"	Slate coloured soil

1. Sarkar and Chatterjee, *This Journal*, 1961, **38**, 725.
2. Sarkar and Chatterjee,—*Ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 948.
3. Sarkar and Chatterjee,—*Bull Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1964, **26**, 184.
4. Marshall and Jeffries,—*Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1945, **10**, 397.

TABLE II

Chemical composition of Clays (original and oxide-free)

		% loss on ignition	% SiO ₂	% Al ₂ O ₃	% Fe ₂ O ₃	% TiO ₂	% CaO	% MgO	% Na ₂ O	% K ₂ O	% SiO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃ molar ratio.
Bankura	Original	12.99	41.78	28.10	11.82	0.90	0.28	0.24	—	3.76	2.52
	Oxide-free	12.46	50.63	27.92	5.09	0.85	0.29	0.28	—	2.82	3.08
Suri	Original	10.53	45.78	27.26	11.76	1.13	trace	0.14	—	2.92	2.84
	Oxide-free	12.26	50.34	28.53	5.81	0.63	—	0.20	—	3.11	2.99
Bangalore	Original	14.11	40.07	34.07	10.59	0.69	0.98	0.27	—	0.13	1.99
	Oxide-free	13.77	44.46	35.49	4.92	0.45	0.41	0.32	—	0.15	2.12
Anantapur	Original	12.14	43.78	25.20	15.67	0.95	0.25	0.48	—	1.34	2.84
	Oxide-free	10.68	49.82	28.26	7.27	1.36	0.34	0.53	—	1.48	2.99
Padegaon	Original	10.88	51.02	17.85	14.04	0.91	0.62	4.41	0.18	0.33	4.85
	Oxide-free	11.32	65.07	10.74	6.41	1.03	0.75	4.50	0.20	0.31	10.28
Kalimpong	Original	11.04	45.90	21.84	14.11	0.94	0.36	0.12	0.21	5.28	3.56
	Oxide-free	9.39	57.93	19.95	5.15	1.10	0.42	0.20	0.16	5.35	4.92
Berhampore	Original	8.75	46.40	22.82	12.99	0.81	0.50	0.39	0.15	6.42	3.44
	Oxide-free	8.90	61.53	17.41	4.50	0.96	0.31	0.22	0.10	6.18	5.99
Uluberia	Original	12.32	44.58	22.56	12.50	1.07	0.42	0.55	—	5.93	3.35
	Oxide-free	9.74	52.20	23.24	7.84	1.20	0.38	0.61	—	5.62	3.81

The results of chemical analysis of H-form of soil clays, original and oxide-free have been cited in Table II. From the analytical data, SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratio, K₂O and MgO contents and loss on ignition values of H-clays, both original and oxide-free, it appears that Bankura and Suri clays contain appreciable amounts of illite, as high amounts of potassium in these H-clays would suggest but Bangalore clay contains a small amount of K₂O (0.13—0.15%) and show a SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratio between 1.99 and 2.12. This clearly indicates that Bangalore clay is predominantly kaolinitic. Anantapur clay contains 1.34—1.48% K₂O and 0.48—0.53% MgO which indicate the presence of illite and possibly a small amount of montmorillonite. Padegaon clay contains 4.41—4.50% MgO, 0.31—0.33% K₂O indicating the presence of monimorillonite as the major constituent with a low percentage of illite. The high SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratio (4.85) of this clay appears to be due to the presence of an appreciable amount of quartz⁵ in the original clay as well as a preferential removal of free Al₂O₃ compared to SiO₂ during the treatment by Marshall and Jeffries method. Berhampore, Kalimpong and Uluberia clays give K₂O content between 5.28 and 6.42 percent, indicating that these three clays are mainly illitic in nature. In these calculations the assumption has been made that all the potassium in the H-clays comes from illite and all the magnesium from montmorillonite an assumption which may not be valid in all cases. All the eight soil clays studied contain high percentages of Fe₂O₃ ranging from 10.59 to 15.67 percent, but after removal of free-oxides, Fe₂O₃ contents come down to 4.50—7.84 percent.

The results of X-ray analysis of the glycerol solvated soil clays (White and Jackson⁶) have been presented in Table III and that of oxide-free clay in Table IIIA.

5. Bagchi, *Indian Soc. Soil Sci. Bull.* No. 1951, 6, 29.

6. White and Jackson, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1946, 11, 150.

TABLE III

X-ray diffraction data of soil clays (glycerol solvated)

Bankura		Suri		Bangalore		Anantapur		Padegaon		Kalimpong		Berhampore		Uluberia	
d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I
10.10	.1	10.10	.1	7.106	10	7.12	1	18.42	10B	10.01	3	10.01	3	9.90	3
7.19	1	7.144	2	4.45	7VB	4.45	10B	10.50	2	4.482	8B	4.482	8B	4.473	8
4.45	10B	4.465	10B	4.32	1	3.328	3	4.50	8	4.26	1	4.262	2	4.248	2
4.23	1	4.25	2	4.15	3	2.558	5	3.335	4	3.342	10	3.35	10	3.342	10
4.13	3	4.15	4	3.57	10	2.501	2	2.567	4	3.195	1	2.572	7B	2.57	6B
3.54	3VB	3.56	2	3.334	2	1.487	5VB	2.144	1	2.57	6B	2.458	2	2.459	2
3.334	8	3.518	2	2.56	3			1.506	5VB	2.133	2	2.368	2	2.394	2
2.564	6B	3.334	10	2.49	3					1.505	5VB	2.29	1	2.133	1
2.42	1	2.558	6	2.336	4							2.133	2	1.535	2
2.325	1	2.49	1	2.29	3							1.53	2	1.503	5VB
1.813	1	2.34	1	1.988	1							1.506	5VB		
1.495	5	2.29	1	1.66	1										
1.369	1VB	1.817	2	1.487	5VB										
		1.496	5VB												

d—interplanar spacings in Å unit. I—intensities of the reflections, estimated with respect to the strongest reflection of the pattern as 10.

B—Broad, VB—Very Broad.

TABLE III A

X-ray diffraction data of the oxide-free soil clays (glycerol solvated)

Bankura		Suri		Bangalore		Anantapur		Padegaon		Kalimpong		Berhampore		Uluberia	
d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I
10.00	1	10.00	0.5	7.20	10B	7.22	0.1*	10.51	7B	10.00	5	10.02	5	10.06	5
7.27	2B	7.21	5	4.47	7	4.47	10	7.16	1	7.19	2	7.15	3	7.23	2
4.48	9B	4.48	9B	4.18	3	4.27	1	4.48	8B	5.01	1.5	4.98	2	5.00	1
4.26	3	4.26	3	3.58	9B	3.52	0.1	4.26	3	4.99	7B	4.48	8B	4.48	8B
3.54	0.1	3.58	3	3.34	3.5	3.34	9	4.14	0.1	4.26	5	4.26	4	4.26	4
3.34	10	3.53	1	2.57	6	2.56	2	4.03	0.1	4.12	0.1	4.13	0.5	4.13	0.1
2.99	0.1	3.34	10	2.54	2	2.52	0.1	3.68	0.1	3.88	2	4.00	0.1	3.88	1.5
2.60	0.1	3.01	0.1	2.50	6	2.34	0.1	3.52	0.5	3.74	2	3.88	1	3.75	1
2.57	7B	2.60	0.1	2.38	0.5	2.28	0.1*	3.34	10	3.59	0.1	3.75	1.5	3.59	0.1
2.50	0.1	2.57	7B	2.35	9B	2.17	0.1*	3.21	1	3.50	4	3.58	0.1	3.51	2
2.42	0.1	2.50	0.5	2.30	5	2.13	0.1*	3.01	0.1	3.34	10	3.50	3	3.34	10
2.39	0.1	2.46	0.5	2.00	3	1.67	0.1*	2.59	1.5	3.25	0.1	3.34	10	3.21	2
2.34	0.1	2.41	0.5	1.94	0.1	1.54	0.1*	2.57	2	3.20	2.5	3.25	0.5	2.99	1.5
2.29	0.1	2.34	2	1.90	0.1	1.49	4	2.46	2	3.00	4	3.21	2	2.82	1.5
2.23	0.1	2.29	1.5	1.85	0.1	1.29	0.1*	2.38	1.5B	2.86	2.5	2.99	2	2.80	1
2.12	0.1	2.24	0.5	1.78	0.1					2.80	2	2.87	1.5		
1.82	4	2.13	1	1.69	0.5					2.59	4	2.80	1		
1.54	0.1	1.94	0.1B	1.67	1					2.57	7				
1.50	5														

B=Broad, VB=Very Broad, *Very indistinct. d—interplanar spacings in Å units; I—intensities of the reflections, estimated with respect to strongest reflection of the pattern as 10.

The X-ray diffraction pattern of Bankura clay (original) shows characteristic reflections at 10.10 Å, 7.19 Å and 3.54 Å while the oxide-free clay at 10.0 Å, 7.27 Å and 3.54 Å respectively corresponding to (001) line of illite, and (001) and (002) spacings of kaolinite. Thus, Bankura clay seems to be a mixture of illite and kaolinite. Intensity measurements show that 10 Å line is comparatively weak compared to 7.27 Å line (broad) and thus indicates the relative abundance of kaolinite compared to illite. Suri clays (original and oxide-free) show lines at 10.10 Å and 7.144 Å and at 10.0 Å and 7.21 Å respectively which are characteristic of (001) lines of illite and kaolinite respectively. The intensity of lines for the illite around 10.0 Å is weaker compared to those around 7.20 Å, suggesting that Suri clay also is a mixture of kaolinite and illite, the proportion of kaolinite being higher. The strong reflections at 7.106 Å and 3.57 Å observed in the case of Bangalore clay (original) and at 7.20 Å and 3.58 Å in oxide-free clay suggest that this clay is predominantly kaolinitic. Anantapur clay (original) shows very weak reflection at 7.12 Å corresponding to the (001) spacing of kaolinite. The (002) spacing of kaolinite could not be observed in this clay. Oxide-free clay also shows very weak reflections at 7.22 Å and 3.52 Å. Since reflection beyond 7.22 Å are also not perceptible, the 7.22 Å line seems to correspond to poorly crystallised kaolinite. Glycerol solvated Padegaon clay (original) gives strong lines at 18.42 Å and also at 10.50 Å but the 18 Å line could not be detected in the X-ray diffraction pattern of the oxide-free sample. This cannot be ascribed to the decomposition of montmorillonite as the exchange capacities of the oxide free clays are higher than those of the original clays (Table V). A weak reflection at 7.16 Å is, however, observed in the oxide-free clay. The 10.50 Å line seems to be due to shifting of 10 Å line of illite owing to the presence of montmorillonite (Brydon and Marshall⁷). These data suggest that Padegaon clay contains both montmorillonite and illite and probably a very small amount of kaolinite. The X-ray diffraction patterns of Kalimpong, Berhampore and Uluberia original and oxide-free clays shows reflection at 10.01 Å, 10.01 Å, 9.90 Å and at 10.0 Å, 10.02 Å and 10.06 Å respectively. The second order lines of illite viz., 5.01 Å, 4.98 Å and 5.00 Å have also been observed in the three oxide-free clays respectively. Besides these, oxide-free Kalimpong, Berhampore and Uluberia clays show weak reflections at 7.19 Å and 3.50 Å; at 7.23 Å and 3.51 Å and 7.23 Å and 3.51 Å respectively, which are characteristic of (001) and (002) lines of kaolinite. It appears, therefore, that these three clays contain illite as dominant clay mineral with a small amount of kaolinite. The X-ray diffraction data of the soil clays indicate that characteristic basal reflections in some cases are less pronounced. This may be due partly to the fine particle size. Removal of free-oxides from the soil clays has been generally found to improve the intensity of the basal reflections in some cases. But in Padegaon clay the 18 Å line due to montmorillonite could not be observed after removal of oxide from this clay.

Differential thermal analysis (D.T.A.) were carried out in an apparatus which was patterned after the design of Berkelheimer⁸. The H-clays (dried at 105° for 16 hours) were used for D. T. A. The D.T.A. data of clays both original and oxide-free have been presented in Table IV. Bankura clay (original) shows endothermic peaks at 130°, 310-320° (weak) and 560° respectively and an exothermic peak at 900°. Bankura oxide-free clay, however, shows endothermic peaks at 140°, 550-560° and exothermic peak at

7. *Research Bull. Missouri Agric. Expt. Sta.*, 1957, No. 623.

8. *Report of Investigation*, U.S. Department of Interior Bureau of Mines, 1944.

TABLE IV

D.T.A. results of soil clays (H-Clays)

Clay	Endothermic peaks at temp°	Exothermic peaks at temp°.	Remarks
Bankura	Original—130, 310-320, 560	900	Endothermic peaks at 130° and 560° are very sharp. Peak at 900° is well distinct.
	Oxide-free—140, 550-560	910	Exothermic peak is quite distinct but small.
Suri	Original—150, 570	910	Endothermic peaks and also exothermic peaks are well distinct.
	Oxide-free—140, 560-570	920-930	Peak at 560-570° is distinctly sharp.
Bangalore	Original—120-140, 580	945	Peaks at 580° and also at 945° are very sharp.
	Oxide-free—110, 580-590	960	Endothermic peak at 110° is small. Exothermic peak at 580-590° and exothermic peak at 960° is sharp.
Anantapur	Original—170-180, 560-570, 680	910	Peaks at 560-570°, 170-180° and 910° are well distinct.
	Oxide-free—160, 560	910	Peaks at 560° and 910° are distinctly sharp.
Padegaon	Original—200, 550-560, 840	410, 860	Peaks at 200°, 840° and 860° are clear and well defined.
	Oxide-free—140-150, 500-510, 650	350-360, 890	Peak at 140-150° is sharp but 650° endothermic peak is very weak.
Kalimpong	Original—150, 550-560	390, 890-900	Endothermic peaks and exothermic peaks are clear.
	Oxide-free—130, 530-540	370-380, 950-960	Peak at 950-960° is not well distinct.
Berhampore	Original—150, 560	900-910	Peaks are distinct.
	Oxide-free—140, 540	950	950° peak is not clear.
Uluberia	Original—150, 560	910	Peaks are well defined.
	Oxide-free—140, 540	900-910	900-910° peak is weak.

910°. The first endothermic peak at 130° (140°) indicates the presence of illite. The second (third) endothermic peak at 560° may be due to illite. The high temperature endothermic peak i.e. third endothermic peak near the 900°, which is characteristic of 2:1 lattice type of mineral is absent. This is probably due to the presence of kaolinite in the illitic clay (Sarkar and Chatterjee^{1,2}). The very weak endothermic peak at 310-320° observed in the original clay may probably be due to montmorillonite. But no such endothermic peak is observed in the oxide-free clay. From characteristic endothermic peaks, it appears that Suri clay contains illite as one of the constituents. The endothermic peak round about 900° is absent. Suri clay also contains kaolinite as one of its constituents which probably affects the 900° endothermic peak^{1,2}. The sharp endothermic peak at 580° and exothermic peak in 945° in Bangalore (original) and sharp endothermic peak at 580-590° and almost sharp exothermic peak at 960° in case of oxide-free clay suggest that Bangalore clay contains kaolinite as the dominant clay mineral. The D. T. A. diagrams of Bangalore clay (both original and oxide-free) shows a very weak endothermic peak between 110° and 140°, which may be probably due to the presence of a small amount of illite. The D.T.A. curve

of Anantapur clay show three endothermic peaks at 170-180°, 560-570° and 680° (weak) respectively and exothermic peak at 910°. The oxide-free Anantapur clay gives endothermic peaks at 160°, 560° respectively and exothermic peak at 910°. The endothermic peak at 680° could not be detected in the oxide-free clay. The first two endothermic peaks are due to the presence of illite and third one in the original clay at 680° indicates the presence of small amount of montmorillonite, which suffers decomposition during the removal of the free oxide. Padegaon clay shows endothermic peak at 200°, 550-560° and 840° respectively and an exothermic peak at 860°. Padegaon oxide free clays shows endothermic peak at 140-150°, 500-510° and 650° (very weak) respectively. The 650° endothermic peak though very weak indicates the presence of montmorillonite. The oxide-free clay shows exothermic peak at 890°. Padegaon clay both original and oxide-free shows another exothermic peak at a temperature between 350° and 410° which may be attributed to the decomposition of small amount of organic material which escaped oxidation on treatment with H₂O₂. The feature of D.T.A. curves of Padegaon clay thus suggest that this clay is a mixture of montmorillonite and illite. The D.T.A. data obtained with Kalimpong, Berhampur and Uluberia clays suggest that these three clays are predominantly illitic in nature but they also contain some amount of kaolinite.

The results of potentiometric titration of H-forms of soil clays (original and oxide-free) with KOH and Ca(OH)₂ have been shown in Table V.

TABLE V

Total acidities of the soil clays (original and oxide-free) at their inflection points

Soil clay†.	Base	Total acid m.e. of base per 100 grams of clay					
		Potentiometric curves (original clay)			Potentiometric curves (Oxide-free clay)		
		1st Inflection	2nd Inflection	3rd Inflection	1st Inflection	2nd Inflection	3rd Inflection
Bankura	KOH	40.0 (8.2)*	82.0 (10.8)	—	44.0 (7.7)*	114.0 (10.1)	—
	Ca(OH) ₂	44.0 (8.6)	86.0 (11.0)	—	40.0 (7.4)	124.0 (10.3)	—
Suri	KOH	32.0 (8.1)	82.0 (10.1)	—	32.0 (8.0)	84.0 (9.9)	—
	Ca(OH) ₂	40.0 (7.8)	90.0 (10.1)	—	36.0 (7.2)	114.0 (10.2)	—
Bangalore	KOH	12.5 (8.0)	37.0 (9.9)	—	13.0 (7.7)	41.0 (9.7)	—
	Ca(OH) ₂	15.0 (8.6)	35.0 (10.6)	—	12.5 (7.6)	24.0 (9.4)	—
Anantapur	KOH	44.0 (8.2)	92.0 (10.2)	—	44.0 (7.6)	106.0 (10.1)	—
	Ca(OH) ₂	52.0 (7.7)	105.0 (10.2)	—	42.0 (6.7)	100.0 (10.2)	—
Padegaon	KOH	46.0 (7.2)	130.0 (9.4)	—	54.0 (7.4)	140.0 (9.7)	—
	Ca(OH) ₂	46.0 (7.0)	—	—	54.0 (6.6)	—	—
Kalimpong	KOH	38.0 (6.7)	74.0 (9.1)	112.0 (10.0)	28.0 (7.2)	146.0 (9.6)	—
	Ca(OH) ₂	46.0 (6.4)	90.0 (8.8)	126.0 (10.1)	34.0 (7.2)	—	—
Berhampur	KOH	47.0 (8.1)	114.0 (10.6)	—	20.0 (6.8)	36.0 (8.6)	107.0 (9.5)
	Ca(OH) ₂	50.0 (7.4)	—	—	20.0 (6.8)	88.0 (9.3)	—
Uluberia	KOH	48.0 (7.7)	94.0 (9.5)	—	30.0 (8.6)	156.0 (10.5)	—
	Ca(OH) ₂	54.0 (7.4)	—	—	46.0 (7.1)	138.0 (9.8)	—

*Figures within bracket denote pH at inflection.

The potentiometric titration curves of H-form of Bankura H-clay (original) show two inflection points with KOH and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. Total acidities at the inflection points and also pH at inflection are higher in case of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ titration curve. The ratio of about 2.0 of total acids at the first and second inflection points suggests the presence of kaolinitic in the Bankura clay (Mukherjee and Mitra⁹). Oxide-free Bankura clay shows, however, dibasic acid character, inflection points occurring at lower pH, and the total acidity at second inflection is much greater than that observed with the original clay. Comparing the features of potentiometric curves, the number of inflection points in the pH curves, the pH at inflection and ratio of total acids at the inflection points, with those of prepared binary and ternary mixtures, it appears that Bankura clay contains 2:1 lattice type of clay minerals along with kaolinite (Sarkar and Chatterjee¹⁰). The inflection point around pH 10 observed in the potentiometric curves may be due to the presence of illite in this clay (Mitra and Rajagopalan⁹). The high total acidity observed at the first inflection point suggests the presence of montmorillonite in Bankura clay. The potentiometric titration curve of Sauri H-clay (original) shows two inflections with KOH and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, the ratio of total acidities at the two inflection points being respectively 2.5 and 2.2. The results with oxide-free Sauri H-clay are also in accord with the dibasic nature of the clay. Bangalore clay exhibits two inflection points in the pH curve with KOH and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, the ratio of total acidities at the two inflection being 2.96 and 2.3 respectively. Oxide free Bangalore H-clay with KOH and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ also show a dibasic character. The pH's observed at the inflection are lower than those observed in Bangalore original H-clay. The features of the potentiometric titration curve indicate that it is mainly kaolinitic clay. Anantapur clays (original and oxide-free) show a dibasic nature, the pH at inflections being lower with oxide-free clays. The ratio of the total acidities at the inflection points is between 2.0 and 2.1 with original H-clay but is around 2.4 in case of oxide-free clay. The titration curves of H-form of Padegaon clay with KOH show two inflections but show only one with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$.

The potentiometric titration curves of the oxide-free Padegaon H-clay show similar features but the total acidities observed at the inflection points are higher than those of the original clay. The potentiometric titration curves of Kalimpong H-clay (original) with KOH and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ show three inflection points. The ratio of total acidities at the first two inflection points is around 2.0 and that at the second and third points is around 1.5. The characteristic features of the potentiometric titration show the illitic nature of the clay (Mitra and Rajagopalan⁹). Kalimpong H-clay after removal of free-oxide shows two inflection points when titrated with KOH but one inflection with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. The titration curves of H-clay from Berhampur soil with KOH show two inflection points, the ratio of the total acidities at the inflection points being 2.3 but with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ only one inflection point is shown. The titration curves of the oxide-free Berhampore clay shows three inflection points with KOH, whereas titration curves with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ show only two inflection points. Uhuberia clay (original) gives two inflection with KOH but with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ only one inflection. The oxide-free H-clay shows two inflections with KOH and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. The total acidity at the second inflection point with KOH titration is much higher compared to that of the original clay. The ratio of total acidities obtained from the KOH titration curve is about 2.0 with original clay, whereas it is around 3.0 with the oxide-free clay.

9. *J. Colloid Sci.* 1946, 1, 141.

10. *Nature*, 1948, 162, 104.

TABLE VI

Clays isolated from soils from	X-ray data	D.T.A. data	Chemical analysis	Electrochem. studies.	viscosity measurement.
Bankura (laterite)	K I	K I	I K (?)*	K I M	K M
Suri (laterite)	K I	K I	I K (?)*	K I M	K M
Bangalore (red)	K	K I(?)	K	K I	K
Anantapur (red)	K	I K	I M K (?)	I M K(?)	I K(?)
Padegaon (black)	M I K(?)	M I	M I	M I	M
Kalinpong (alluvial)	I K	I	I M(?)	I M(?)	I M(?)
Berhampur (alluvial)	I K	I	I K(?)	I M(?)	I
Uluberia (alluvial)	I K	I	I M(?)	I M(?)	I M

N.B. K, I, and M denote respectively Kaolinite, Illite, and Montmorillonite.

*Sign of interrogation (?) indicates doubtful existence.

Viscosity Measurement: The variation of viscosity with gradual addition of KOH to the hydrogen clays (original and oxide-free) has been studied. Viscosity-base concentration curve of Bankura clay shows initially a fall in viscosity and then the viscosity rises to a maximum around 75% neutralisation and finally it decreases. After removal of free oxides, the features of the viscosity-base concentration curve remain more or less the same. The results suggest that Bankura clay is a mixture of kaolinite and montmorillonite (Mitra and Mukherjee⁸). Suri clay shows a slow rise in the viscosity up to 50-60% neutralisation and the viscosity at higher neutralisation decreases to a constant value. But after removal of free oxides, viscosity of Suri H-clay initially decreases up to about 40% neutralisation (characteristic of kaolinite) and then gradually rises to a maximum at about 65-70% neutralisation (characteristic of montmorillonite) and finally it decreases. Suri clay may thus be assumed to be a mixture of kaolinite and montmorillonite. Viscosity of Bangalore clay shows a rapid fall with gradual addition of alkali up to neutralisation point and then becomes constant. The oxide-free clay also shows the same characteristics. These features indicate that Bangalore clay is predominantly a kaolinitic clay. With gradual addition of alkali to Anantapur clay, viscosity shows an initial fall and then rises to a maximum at about 50-60% neutralisation and finally decreases. After removal of free-oxides from Anantapur clay, viscosity base concentration curve shows a rise to a maximum at about 40% neutralisation and then the viscosity rapidly falls. These characteristics indicate the presence of kaolinite, illite and montmorillonite in the clay from Anantapur soil. The viscosity-base saturation curve of H-clay from Padegaon soil suggests the presence of montmorillonite as major clay mineral constituent in it. Vis-

viscosity-base saturation curve of Kalimpong H-clay shows a maximum at about 25-30% neutralisation and another at 60% neutralisation. The curve for oxide-free Kalimpong H-clay rises to a maximum at about 50-55% neutralisation and then gradually falls to a constant value. The features of the viscosity-alkali concentration curves suggest that Kalimpong clay contains illite with some amount of montmorillonite. Berhampore H-clay shows a gradual rise in viscosity up to about 85-90% neutralisation (characteristic of montmorillonite). But after removal of free oxides, the viscosity-base saturation curve of this clay shows a maximum at about 40% neutralisation indicating the presence of illite. Viscosity of Uluberia H-clay rises up to 60-70% neutralisation with gradual addition of KOH and shows no appreciable variation. But after removal of free oxides, Uluberia clay shows characteristic features of both illite and montmorillonite.

Conclusions on the clay mineralogical compositions of the clays used in the present investigation derived from the results of chemical, X-ray, differential thermal, electrochemical and viscosity measurements have been summarised in Table VI.

Data presented in this paper indicate that removal of free oxides does not materially alter the mineralogical compositions of H-clays. It is also observed that conclusions on the clay mineralogical compositions of clays should be based on the results of a combination of measurements.

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